

Impact Study

Forensics

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Context

Since the 1980s, DNA evidence has been used to solve crimes. Increasingly, this encompasses environmental and wildlife DNA, as well as that from humans, as demonstrated by governments starting to add dedicated [wildlife forensics laboratories](#) to their existing human DNA forensic capabilities.

This case study explores how biodata resources and DNA databases are supporting criminal investigations and wildlife protection. From environmental DNA revealing a suspect's presence to specialised databases protecting endangered species, these examples show how biological data is becoming central to modern law enforcement.

Matching suspects and crime scenes using DNA metabarcoding

DNA evidence has fundamentally changed the [nature of criminal investigations](#) since the 1980s — for example, supporting the exoneration of a suspect and the conviction of [Colin Pitchfork](#) in 1986, thanks to the early work of [Alec Jeffreys](#). Since then, even high-profile cold cases like the [Golden State Killer](#) have been solved through DNA databases and genetic genealogy.

Molecular phylogenetics—the study of evolutionary relationships through genetic sequencing—has emerged as a powerful tool in forensic science, particularly in cases involving the intentional transmission of infectious diseases. [Two landmark U.S. criminal trials](#) illustrate how this method has been used to support legal outcomes by tracing the genetic lineage of HIV-1 strains.

In *Washington State v. Anthony Eugene Whitfield* (2004), the defendant was accused of knowingly exposing multiple women to HIV without disclosing his status. Investigators collected viral samples from Whitfield and several of the women with whom he had sexual contact. Phylogenetic analysis revealed a paraphyletic relationship: the women’s HIV strains were genetically nested within the diversity of Whitfield’s strain, strongly suggesting he was the source of the infections.

To validate the findings, researchers compared the sequences to a broader set of HIV samples from GenBank, using the BLAST tool, and confirmed the distinctiveness of the cluster. This scientific evidence, alongside medical and testimonial records, contributed to Whitfield’s conviction on 17 counts of first-degree assault with sexual motivation, resulting in a 178-year prison sentence.

A similar approach was used in *State of Texas v. Philippe Padieu* (2009), where multiple women who had no prior connection to one another discovered they were HIV-positive after relationships with the same man.

Phylogenetic analysis of the viral sequences from the women and Padieu once again showed that the women’s strains formed a tight genetic cluster, with Padieu’s strain at the root—indicating he was the likely source.

The analysis was further supported by comparisons with carefully selected unrelated HIV sequences from GenBank using the BLAST tool, ensuring the cluster was not part of a broader local outbreak. This evidence was instrumental in Padieu’s conviction on six counts of aggravated assault with a deadly weapon, for which he received multiple 45-year prison sentences.

Identifying the scene of a crime through pollen analysis

When human DNA is not available to investigators, they must turn to alternative sources of biological evidence like soil, pollen and dust. The concept of using pollen in forensic investigations is not [new](#), but research at the National Center for Forensic Science, University of Central Florida is making it easier to track criminals.

While work is still in its early stages, researchers have been able to [develop an approach](#) that would allow the detection of particular pollen and the tracing of this back to specific trees or locations. Critically, the researchers devised a way to extract pollen DNA without destroying the grain itself. This innovation allows more DNA to be tested from a single sample while preserving the pollen grains as critical evidence for potential court proceedings. The PhD thesis '[Genomic Analysis of Pollen Grains for Forensic Applications](#)' outlines these concepts and recognises the importance of NCBI's GenBank and the BLASTn and megaBLAST algorithms.

Using this approach, DNA analysis can identify a plant with far more quantifiable certainty than was possible previously and it can even be performed in the field. These advances suggest there will be future developments in fighting crime with pollen.

DNA fingerprinting to combat animal trafficking

More than [4,000 species](#) around the world are being targeted by wildlife traffickers.

Population losses caused by trafficking can be devastating, triggering ecosystem-level impacts by disturbing interdependencies between different species.

Scientists have been using DNA fingerprinting — a technique once reserved for human crime scenes — to combat the [multibillion-dollar](#) wildlife trafficking industry. In South Africa, this forensic innovation helped bring down a notorious poaching ring.

The breakthrough came when researchers discovered they could extract DNA from rhinoceros horns which was previously thought to be impossible. By drilling into the horn's core, they could access DNA from dead cells. This technique was crucial in the case of Campbell, a white rhinoceros killed on a private reserve in June 2016.

When authorities arrested the Ndlovu Gang days later at a resort in Grahamstown, they seized critical evidence: a freshly removed rhino horn and a bloody saw. Investigators extracted DNA from both items and compared it against [RhODIS](#), South Africa's rhinoceros DNA database containing over 100,000 genetic fingerprints. Since 2012, South African law has required DNA sampling from all rhino handling, meaning Campbell's profile was already on file. The match was definitive and this evidence, combined with cellphone records and ballistics analysis, built a case that led to the conviction of all three gang members.

Another example of genetic forensics solving wildlife crimes comes from Israel. Rangers discovered mountain gazelle [DNA on the muzzles of hunting dogs](#) and matched dog hairs from a suspect's vehicle to these same animals. This meant that criminal charges could be made even without recovering the carcass.

Conclusions

These case studies demonstrate how biological databases and DNA technologies are changing forensic science across different contexts.

As DNA reference databases grow more comprehensive, and sequencing technologies continue to advance, the potential for biological evidence to solve complex cases will likely expand. DNA analysis will be an indispensable tool for law enforcement in the 21st century.

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Appendix – Resources discussed

Resources	About
GenBank	GenBank is the NIH's comprehensive genetic sequence database. GenBank provides an annotated collection of all publicly available DNA sequences. As part of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration, GenBank shares data with other organisations on a daily basis to provide access for the scientific community to the most comprehensive and up-to-date DNA sequence information.
RefSeq	The Reference Sequence (RefSeq) is a collection of annotated sequences provided by the National Library of Medicine. The collection covers genomic DNA, proteins and transcripts, and forms a foundation for functional, medical and diversity studies. This resource provides a reference for genome annotation, gene identification and mutation analysis. Bacteria, archaea and viruses are included in the database.
RhODIS	RhODIS is a central, secure database of rhino DNA profiles for forensic purposes, also a traceability system for individual rhinos and horns. This database stores a unique genetic fingerprint for every rhino that has been sampled. The method uses genetic sequences to create a fingerprint or barcode that is unique to each animal. Barcodes include a gender marker and a species marker that can differentiate between black and white rhinos. The technique uses less than 20mg of DNA per horn (a very small amount) and so accurate that it can be used as evidence in court cases.

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